

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: Thermal Conductivity of Metal Hydrides in Hydrogen Pressure.

This Application Highlight illustrates C-Therm's unique capabilities in characterizing metal hydrides using a combination of C-Therm's high-pressure cell designs and transient thermal conductivity measurement methods. The thermal conductivities of titanium-iron-manganese (TiFeMn) metal hydride were measured using the TLS (powder) and TPS (pellets) methods. The samples were tested in vacuum, ambient, and 6.9 bar hydrogen atmospheres.

Hydrogen has been increasingly studied as a clean and efficient energy source in the last decade. However, many constraints, such as energy density and safety concerns, still impede practical applications. Metal hydrides offer potential advantages in capacity, safety, and long-term stability. Metal hydrides can be used for various applications ranging from hydrogen storage in mobile and stationary applications to purification, (isotope) separation, thermal storage, and heat pumps.¹

Figure 1 Importance of thermal behavior of metal hydrides during absorption and release of hydrogen.

However, metal hydride powder's low inherent thermal conductivity significantly limits the hydrogenation/dehydrogenation process in the metal hydride bed. Characterizing the influencing factors on the effective thermal conductivity of a metal hydride bed, such as atmospheric conditions (pressure and gas), plays an important role in guiding the optimization design of heat and mass transfer structure of metal hydride hydrogen storage devices, as seen in Figure 1. It is also important to note that the effective thermal conductivity of the hydride bed under working conditions is not static but dynamically changed by the combined influence of multiple factors.^{2,3}

Figure 2 C-Therm 6 mm Thermal Conductivity Sensor (Left). Pelletized form of TiFeMn Hydride (Right).

¹ Li et al, RSC Adv., 2022, 12, 25722, DOI: 10.1039/d2ra04627j

² Bao et al, Int. J. Hydrog. Energy, 2020, 45, 11, 6680, DOI: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.12.185

³ Yang, Huot et al, Int. J. Hydrog. Energy, 2022, 47, 11236 DOI: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.01.141

The FLEX Transient Plane Source (TPS) method available on the Trident platform has been used to measure the thermal conductivity of pelletized TiFeMn hydride. The 6mm TPS sensor, shown in Figure 2, was placed between two identical pellets and clamped together. The sensor-sample setup is then placed inside the pressure vessel. The pellets' thermal conductivity was then measured at room temperature under different atmospheric conditions (air, vacuum, H₂ pressure).

Figure 3 Thermal Conductivity of pelletized TiFeMn hydride under ambient, vacuum, and pressurized hydrogen atmospheres (gauge pressures).

Upon removal of the atmosphere, shown in Figure 3, the TiFeMn pellets' thermal conductivity is measured to be $0.69 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ after maintaining the vacuum (Step 1) for about 5 minutes. Next, the ambient air atmosphere (Step 2) is restored, and the pellet's thermal conductivity increases to $1.77 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$. Inducing the vacuum again (Step 3), the thermal conductivity is measured to be $0.70 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$, repeating the measurements from Step 1. Applying 6.9 bar of hydrogen gas (Step 4), the thermal conductivity drastically increases to $5.44 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ – measurements were collected 5-10 minutes after the increased pressure.⁴

Venting the hydrogen pressure to ambient (Step 5) decreased the thermal conductivity to $3.01 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$, which is noticeably higher when under ambient air. This is most likely due to the contribution of hydrogen to the pellet's overall thermal conductivity.⁵ The different atmosphere conditions (Steps 6 to 9) were then repeated, and the measured thermal conductivities matched the previous measurements.

Similar experiments were done testing the powder forms of the TiFeMn hydride samples using the 50 mm Transient Line Source (TLS) need probe, as shown in Figure 4. The powder sample is packed into a cylindrical container and placed into the pressure cell. The needle probe is inserted into the sample, ensuring the powder is centered and there is minimal air gap between the needle and the powder.

⁴ Activation of the metal hydride and absorption of hydrogen is an exothermic event.

⁵ Hydrogen gas $k = 0.186 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ at ambient pressure. Huber, M. and Harvey, A. (2011), Thermal Conductivity of Gases, CRC-Press, Boca Raton, FL, [online], https://tsapps.nist.gov/publication/get_pdf.cfm?pub_id=907540 (Accessed May 15, 2024)

Figure 4 C-Therm's Trident and Thermal Conductivity Needle Probe and Pressure Cell.

Shown in Figure 5, the thermal conductivity of the powder is $0.20 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ under ambient air atmosphere (Step 1). Under a vacuum atmosphere, the thermal conductivity decreases to $0.06 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ (Step 2). Applying 1.4 bar of hydrogen atmosphere, the thermal conductivity of the powder increases to $1.03 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ (Step 3). Applying 6.9 bar of hydrogen atmosphere, the k barely changes ($1.07 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$, Step 4), indicating a saturation point in the hydrogenation of the hydride powder. Removal of the hydrogen altogether decreased the powder's thermal conductivity to $0.07 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$.

Figure 5 Thermal Conductivity of TiFeMn Hydride Powder under different atmospheric conditions using the TLS method.

Trident's FLEX TPS and Needle TLS methods successfully characterized the thermal conductivities of the pelletized and powder TiFeMn hydride under different atmospheric conditions. These studies demonstrate the transient methods' repeatability and capability in measuring the metal hydrides' thermal properties under varying hydrogen pressure, highlighting the impact of such conditions on the metal hydride's thermal properties. **Measuring the thermal conductivities of the metal hydride within expected high-pressure operating conditions is essential in improving the fundamental understanding of their heat transfer capabilities.**

C-Therm wishes to thank Dr. Jacques Huot for lending his expertise and use of facilities at the Institut de recherche sur l'hydrogène at the Université du Québec à Trois-Rivières during this project.

To learn more about C-Therm's Trident thermal conductivity instrument, visit www.TridentThermalConductivity.com